

Synthesis of Quinazolone and Its Derivatives as Potential Fungicides

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Condensation of 4-bromo-2-pyrazolin-5-one with 2-mercapto-3-aryl-quinazol-4-ones afford the 2-mercapto-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-2'-pyrazolin-5-one-4'yl)-3-aryl-4-quinazolones. Their fungitoxicity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae* has been studied.

SIGNIFICANT fungicidal activity of 2-pyrazolin-5-one, against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* and the brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae* has been mentioned previously¹⁻⁴. A study of literature⁵ revealed that quinazolone, which possesses antimalarial activity, has not yet been screened for fungitoxicity. This prompted us to investigate the fungicidal activity of the quinazolone nucleus. On the basis of the significant fungicidal activity associated with 5-pyrazolone nucleus, we thought it would be of interest to synthesise a heterocyclic compound having both the quinazolone and pyrazolone nuclei. The relative fungicidal activity of the compounds having both the pyrazolone and quinazolone nuclei are found to be more than that of the simple quinazolones. Thirteen 2-mercapto-3-substituted phenyl-4-quinazolones were prepared following the procedure reported earlier⁵. The m.p. and analytical data are given in Table 1. 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-monobromo-2-pyrazolin-5-one (Cpd. No.1) and 3-methyl-4-monobromo-2-pyrazolin-5-one (Cpd.No.2) were prepared

following the method reported earlier⁵⁻⁷. The ethanolic solution of 4-monobromo-5-pyrazolone condensed with 2-mercapto-3-substituted phenyl-4-quinazolones in alcoholic alkali produce the 2-mercapto-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-2'-pyrazolin-5'-one-4'yl)-3-substituted phenyl-4-quinazolones. The condensation product shows IR: 1680 cm⁻¹ (>C=O), enolic band is absent. The absence of the enolic band shows that the pyrazolone is present in carbonyl tautomeric form.

All the compounds prepared during the present investigation have been assayed for fungicidal activity using spore germination test at various concentrations using the standard method⁸. The fungicidal activity of the compounds at 1000 ppm concentration are given in Table 1 & 2. All the compounds except Cpd. Nos. 10 show encouraging activity against *P. oryzae*. Cpd. No.1, 3, 6, 7, 8, 23, 24, 35, 37, 40 cause 100% inhibition of *P. oryzae* spore at 1000 ppm concentration. Highest activity is exhibited by Cpd. No. 35, which inhibits 92% spore

TABLE 1—2-MERCAPTO-3-SUBSTITUTED PHENYL-4-QUINAZOLONE

Cpd. No.	Aryl group 'X'	m.p. (°C)	S(%)		%Inhibition germination at 1000 ppm conc.	
			Calc.	Found	<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
3.	Phenyl	304	12.59	12.54	100	71
4.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	253	11.09	11.01	70	52
5.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	291	11.09	10.88	89	78
6.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	268	11.09	10.92	100	44
7.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	287	10.70	10.45	100	61
8.	<i>o</i> -Carboxyl phenyl	288	10.74	10.51	100	50
9.	<i>p</i> -Carboxyl phenyl	230	10.74	10.39	85	63
10.	α -Naphthyl	228	10.52	10.31	50	54
11.	β -Naphthyl	281	10.52	10.36	64	47
12.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	284	11.26	10.98	90	60
13.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	253	11.26	11.02	78	62
14.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	286	11.94	11.69	95	54
15.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	310	10.73	10.62	71	67

* These are the known compounds.

TABLE 2—2-MERCAPTO-(2'-PYRAZOLIN-5'-ONES-4'-YL)-3-ARYLPHENYL-4-QUINAZOLONE

(Cpd. 16-40)

 Y = C₆H₅ (16-28), H (29-40)

Cpd. No.	Aryl group 'X'	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	S%		% Inhibition germination at 1000 ppm conc.	
				Calc.	Found	<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
16.	Phenyl	203	80	7.51	7.38	92	34
17.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	274	70	6.94	6.69	95	42
18.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	193	50	6.94	6.83	90	56
19.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	242	65	6.94	6.78	90	39
20.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	252	55	6.79	6.85	89	47
21.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	250	50	7.01	7.10	97	61
22.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	232	45	7.01	7.21	84	84
23.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	272	50	7.27	7.13	100	56
24.	<i>o</i> -Carboxyl phenyl	240	40	6.80	6.84	100	51
25.	<i>p</i> -Carboxyl phenyl	202	50	6.80	6.92	88	76
26.	α -Naphthyl	174	45	6.72	6.56	98	56
27.	β -Naphthyl	250	40	6.72	6.68	80	38
28.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxy phenyl	286	30	6.80	6.69	85	62
29.	Phenyl	292	75	9.14	9.01	88	39
30.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	284	65	8.32	8.21	94	38
31.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	258	60	8.32	8.42	87	70
32.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	237	55	8.32	8.18	88	68
33.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	279	60	8.37	8.19	84	56
34.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	261	60	8.79	8.61	98	42
35.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	260	35	8.42	8.23	100	48
36.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	247	40	8.42	8.54	78	60
37.	α -Naphthyl	203	45	8.00	7.89	100	40
38.	β -Naphthyl	190	40	8.00	7.91	72	70
39.	<i>o</i> -Carboxyl phenyl	276	50	8.12	8.02	92	41
40.	<i>p</i> -Carboxyl phenyl	218	55	8.12	8.08	100	62

germination at 250 ppm concentration. Seventeen compounds (Cpd. Nos. 2, 3, 5, 7, 9, 12, 13, 15, 21, 22, 25, 28, 31, 32, 36, 38 and 40) show promising activity against *H. oryzae*. Further it was observed that Cpd. No. 22 exhibits highest activity against *H. oryzae* which inhibits 66 and 84% spore germination at 250 and 1000 ppm concentration respectively. The fungicidal activities of the compounds thus synthesised were compared with some standard fungicides like *o*-ethyl-S, S-diphenyl phosphorodithioate (Hinosan 50%) EC, Difolatan 50% WP, Derosal 60% WP which inhibited 95, 98, 87% of *P. oryzae* spore germination respectively at 1000 ppm concentration. We further noticed that the fungicidal activity of the 28 compounds (Cpd. Nos. 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 12, 14, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 23, 24, 25, 26, 29, 30, 31, 32, 34, 35, 37, 39, 40) are good in

comparison with the standard fungicides, hence these can be used as commercial fungicides.

Experimental

2-Mercapto-(2'-pyrazolin-5'-ones-4'-yl)-3-substituted phenyl-4-quinazolone : (Table 2) :

2-Mercapto-3-substituted phenyl-4-quinazolone (0.01 mole) was dissolved in minimum volume of 10% alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution. To this solution 4-monobromo-2-pyrazolin-5-one (0.01 mole) dissolved in minimum quantity of alcohol, was added drop wise with shaking. The reaction mixture after being kept overnight was refluxed for one hr. on water bath. On cooling no solid separated out. Then it was acidified with dil. HCl. The compound

thus precipitated was filtered, washed with water and finally purified with ethanol.

The m.p. and analytical data of the prepared compounds are recorded in Table 2.

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